

THE "YEARBOOK OF THE INSTITUTE OF THE ROMANIAN REVOLUTION OF DECEMBER 1989"- A NEW ACADEMIC JOURNAL WITH INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNIZED SCIENTIFIC VALUE

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The Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989

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According to Law no. 556 of 7 December 2004, the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989 is the only public institution of national interest whose object of activity is the scientific analysis of the premises, development and effects - in political, economic and social terms - of the Romanian Revolution of

December 1989, in order to achieve a documented, objective and comprehensive image of this cardinal event in the contemporary history of Romania.

As a scientific institution of academic rank, since its establishment, the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989 has brought together outstanding personalities in the field of historical scientific research, at the same time constituting a school of initiation and scientific consecration for young historians. Thus, in the almost 20 years of operation, the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989 has become a pole of excellence in professional scientific research, a fact that is reflected in the impressive number of books and scientific articles developed to international standards by the members of the research team.

In the effort of continuous development and promotion of excellence in scientific research, in the year 2023 the management team of the Institute decided to establish a specialized journal in the form of a "Yearbook", a publication intended to capitalize and disseminate in the national and international scientific community the results acquired in the scientific research activity regarding the essential aspects of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989 and the events that contributed to the perfection of its ideals.

Since the conception of this new specialized scientific journal, the aim has been to promote excellence through internationalization, for which rules were imposed on the development and writing of scientific materials in accordance with the highest internationally recognized scientific and academic standards: own web page; permanent scientific college and editorial college; summaries and keywords in English; quality control system and the application of the peer-review procedure; licensing conditions (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License); copyright terms and ethical compliance in scientific research. This was also the reason why, in a relatively short time, the "Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989" received international recognition, being included and indexed in several catalogues of libraries abroad and international scientific databases.

Thus, the "Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989" was included in the catalogues of the libraries of prestigious universities in the United States of America and Canada, among them: Harvard University, Princeton University, University at Buffalo-New York, Berkeley University of California, University of North Texas or Simon Fraser University. It was also included in the catalogues of some libraries in the United Kingdom, among which they can be mentioned: University of Liverpool or University of Edinburgh.

The explicit recognition of the scientific value of the "Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989" is also evident from the fact that it can be found in the Library of Congress, the largest and most important public library, being in fact the national library of the United States of America.

Also, the "Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989" was recognized and promoted by ResearchGate and Academia.edu, two of the most important platforms for academic and scientific communication internationally due to constant concerns regarding the quality and credibility of scientific materials.

Another great achievement consists in the acceptance and inclusion of the "Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989" in WorldCat - the world's largest library catalogue, an international database recognized in the Order of the Minister of National Education and Scientific Research no. 6129/2016 regarding approval of minimum necessary and mandatory standards for conferring academic titles, professional research-development titles, doctoral supervisor and habilitation certificate.

At the same time, it is necessary to highlight the fact that the "Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989" was indexed in several international scientific databases, among which we can mention: EuroPub: Directory of Academic and Scientific Journals; ROAD (Directory of Open Access Resources); ResearchBib (Academic Resource Index); Directory of Research Journals Indexing (DRJI).

Last but not least, it should be remembered that the "Yearbook of the Romanian Revolution Institute of December 1989" has an ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) digital identifier, which allows it to uniquely identify the scientific contributions published in the journal's pages (<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-5006-5978>).

By virtue of the recognition of the scientific value of the "Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution of December 1989", after the publication of the next issue for the year 2024, will also be started the procedures for indexing the journal in other international databases recognized by the Ministry of Education for the History Field, such as: IPS Thomson & Reuters; ERIHPLUS; Purpose; EBSCO; JSTOR; ProQuest; ProjectMuse; CEEOL; Perseus; DOAJ.

This fact will allow the "Yearbook of the Institute of the Romanian Revolution from December 1989" to become a prestigious journal from the main international scientific stream, increasing the quality, impact and international visibility of the research results, offering the whole world a comprehensive picture of the essential aspects of the Romanian Revolution from December 1989 and the events that contributed to the perfection of its ideals.